

**The International Association
of Forensic Toxicologists**

Established 1963

Task Force Report

on Integrating Artificial Intelligence into Forensic Toxicology

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The AI Task Force

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President's Letter

It gives me great pleasure to introduce the report of the first TIAFT Task Force (TTF1), with this inaugural Task Force exploring the potential integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into forensic toxicology. As President of TIAFT, I am pleased our Association has taken a proactive stance in evaluating both the opportunities and challenges presented by this rapidly evolving technology.

The formation of TTF1 was driven by the need to comprehensively assess how AI can enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of toxicological analyses, while also addressing the ethical, legal, and practical considerations unique to our field. The Task Force's remit included:

- Reviewing current applications of AI in forensic toxicology and their effectiveness.
- Evaluating potential advantages such as increased accuracy, improved data management, cost reduction, and expedited workflows.
- Identifying potential disadvantages, including technical limitations, ethical and legal concerns, dependency risks, skill gaps, and security issues.
- Conducting case studies and comparative analyses to highlight real-world outcomes.
- Providing actionable recommendations and guidelines for safe and effective AI integration.

The report presents a balanced and thorough evaluation of AI's role in forensic toxicology that will be invaluable to TIAFT members. Notable outcomes include

- **Expertise Remains Essential:** While AI offers powerful tools for automating tasks and analyzing complex datasets, the expertise of forensic toxicologists is more crucial than ever. The report highlights the risks of automation bias and the need for ongoing training to ensure that scientific rigor and critical thinking remain at the forefront.
- **Risk-Based Approach:** The Task Force recommends a risk-based strategy for AI implementation, prioritizing low-risk applications such as automating repetitive tasks, while exercising caution with high-risk, decision-critical systems.
- **Validation and Governance:** Robust validation protocols and clear governance frameworks are essential for ensuring the reliability and legal defensibility of AI-driven processes.
- **Collaboration and Data Quality:** The success of AI in forensic toxicology depends on high-quality, well-curated data and collaboration across laboratories and jurisdictions.
- **Recommendations for the Future:** The report provides practical guidelines for integrating AI, including the development of programming skills among toxicologists, establishing data governance policies, and fostering international collaboration.

This report marks the beginning of an important conversation for our global community. AI is not a replacement for expertise, but a tool to augment our capabilities. As forensic toxicologists, we must approach its adoption with curiosity, caution, and a commitment to scientific integrity. I encourage all TIAFT members to engage with the findings, participate in ongoing discussions, and contribute to shaping the future of our discipline.

On behalf of TIAFT, I extend my gratitude to the members of TTF1 for their hard work, dedication and insight, and to all who contributed to this comprehensive evaluation. Together, we will ensure that the integration of AI into forensic toxicology serves the cause of justice and scientific excellence.

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September 2025

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The views expressed in this document are solely those of the authors and do not necessarily represent the positions or opinions of TIAFT or any affiliated organizations.

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Summary and Recommendations

AI is a relatively new technology but has been improving rapidly and has great potential in the field of forensic toxicology to be used in many different ways. Because some AI applications are “black boxes” that cannot be interpreted and our field demands accuracy, transparency and legal defensibility, we need to be careful in where and how we use AI. Not all applications carry the same level of risk, and a risk based approach should be used when deciding where AI should be applied first. Low risk tools, such as those that automate administrative or repetitive technical tasks may be good candidates for early development. At the same time, “moon shot” applications that enable things that are impossible to achieve with current techniques, such as accurately determining the cause of death from the metabolome using HRMS screening data or detecting the presence of previously unknown compounds within samples should be pursued in a research context. A global survey of forensic toxicologists revealed widespread concerns about AI’s ethical implications, emphasizing the need for strong professional networks and continued expert development. The validation and on-going performance monitoring of AI systems is essential, especially when they influence casework. Even AI systems designed to include human oversight should be implemented cautiously, as automation bias can undermine that safeguard. Lessons learned from other sectors show that legal complexity and data-related issues are often the cause of discontinuation of AI projects. Clear governance frameworks around the use of AI and data will assist in ensuring that AI projects have the best possible chance to succeed.

Based on the findings of this report, the taskforce recommends the following actions:

1. **Keep training forensic toxicology experts.** It takes time to train experts. Younger professionals are more susceptible to automation bias, so we must invest time and training in educating the next generation of experts. Moreover, those with little or no knowledge of forensic toxicology may rely on AI to interpret findings or prepare for court, which can lead to the spread of misinformation. Forensic toxicology experts are required more than ever to ensure that knowledge in the field remains based on peer-reviewed scientific literature and not on AI hallucinations.
2. **Make programming skills a central and strategic competency for forensic toxicologists.** AI is relatively easy to grasp for a person who understands programming, but it might be hard to critically understand AI without programming skills. Making forensic data AI-ready requires programming skills, and it might be hard to outsource this to other professionals who do not understand our data. Programming skills can be further used to improve the laboratory information management system (LIMS), automate laboratory workflows, and other non-AI tasks that are useful in a forensic laboratory.

3. **Use a risk-based approach to AI implementations.** Define purpose and quality metrics for a task. If the intended AI application is categorized as high-risk, the ten guardrails for high-risk AI projects proposed by the Australian Government or similar could be addressed. If deemed relevant, a risk assessment plan should be developed and documented. The plan should outline the anticipated risks of AI implementation, the efforts taken to mitigate these risks and any quality checks implemented to monitor the risks. Focus initially on applications with low legal complexity relying on single or few data sources. Considering where the technology is today it might be advisable, also from a pedagogical point, to prioritize projects based on needs, i.e. automate repetitive tasks that take up time.
4. **Consider whether the task can be completed without AI.** Many AI systems are non-deterministic, meaning they may produce different outputs from the same input, and the rationale behind a given result or decision can be difficult or impossible to determine. This is also known as the black box problem. Consider if the task could instead be completed using a deterministic algorithm (i.e., If this, then that) or another non-AI method before starting work on any AI project.
5. **Develop AI and data governance policies.** This will provide clarity for staff when developing and using AI tools and ensure compliance with local laws and regulations.
6. **Develop AI collaborations.** AI systems perform better when trained on larger data sets. Modern AI training also requires significant investment in infrastructure as well as advanced technical knowledge. Toxicology labs should consider collaborating by pooling both resources and data to develop more capable models.
7. **Monitor adaptive AI model performance and verify appropriate staff use.** Automated decision support systems can cause overreliance and distrust.
8. **Perform validation in both the AI and forensic toxicology domains.** Any AI component should be first validated in the AI domain to check performance, then again in the forensic toxicology domain where it forms part of a larger workflow. The amount of validation work will depend on the application and the risk.

1. SCOPE

The International Association of Forensic Toxicologists (TIAFT) represents over 1,800 members worldwide, spanning disciplines from legal medicine and pharmacology to law enforcement and sports toxicology. The association fosters global collaboration and advances research in forensic toxicology through shared expertise and coordinated efforts.

In late 2024, TIAFT established the TIAFT Task Force 1 (TTF1) to evaluate the potential use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in forensic toxicology. The task force, formed through an open call for expressions of interest, includes five practicing forensic scientists. Its objective was to evaluate both the potential benefits and drawbacks of integrating AI into the field, with a focus on the potential to improve the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of toxicological analysis and interpretation, as well as to address any potential risks or ethical concerns. The TIAFT President provided a brief outlining the objectives for TTF1 as a guiding document for our work.

All members of the task force are forensic scientists and not machine learning (ML) experts. We have not critically assessed the differences in underlying ML architectures or other technical aspects of AI but focused on real applications. We hope that this report will help qualify discussions on AI in our field.

*First meeting of TIAFT Task Force 1 - Artificial Intelligence,
January 10, 2025.*

2. METHODS

The task force began its work in January 2025. One of our first steps was to conduct an online survey among TIAFT members to assess forensic toxicologists' familiarity with AI. This survey served to maximize the relevance and impact of our efforts. We also reviewed scientific literature and abstracts from earlier TIAFT conferences.

Over the course of eight months, TTFI held regular online meetings and kept continuous online communication. We periodically reported our progress to the TIAFT Board through the President. Our main dissemination channels were the TIAFT Bulletin, this report, and a live ToxPod episode to be recorded at the TIAFT conference in New Zealand 2025.

In the process, we were inspired by the work of other AI task forces. To make the outcome relevant in our field, we tried to make this report specific, with examples and topics particularly relevant for forensic toxicology. AI is a relatively new technology with few documented applications in routine use, for this reason we combine hypothetical with actual examples from both the peer reviewed literature and our own laboratories to cover different themes.

This report begins with a short background section, followed by a showcase of applications of AI relevant to forensic toxicology that serves as an inspiration, then thematic analyses of topics. Finally, we wrap up with conclusions and recommendations from the task force.

In the spirit of transparency, we used large language models (LLMs) such as ChatGPT, Copilot, and Gemini during the preparation of this report. These tools aided with summarizing academic papers, rewording specific sections, and interpreting data. However, all critical thinking including the selection of case studies, formulation of opinions and recommendations, and overall structure of the report was conducted by the task force members. This reflects our view that while current LLM tools can be useful for low-risk, administrative tasks, they are not a substitute for the critical thinking ability and judgement of a domain expert.

3. BACKGROUND

3.1. What are artificial intelligence, machine learning, and deep learning?

AI is commonly understood to mean a computer system capable of performing tasks typically associated with human intelligence such as learning, reasoning, and decision making. This broad definition means that AI comes in many forms, ranging from recommendation algorithms (Netflix) and web search (Google) to complicated computational models such as LLMs (e.g., ChatGPT) or the Nobel prize winning protein structure prediction program AlphaFold. A subset of AI is ML, which uses algorithms that learn from data to improve performance on a given task without being explicitly programmed. ML algorithms can be categorized into supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning involves training a model on labeled data, where the model learns to map inputs to outputs. Unsupervised learning, on the other hand, deals with unlabeled data and aims to find hidden patterns or intrinsic structures within the data. Reinforcement learning involves training models to make sequences of decisions by rewarding desired behaviors and penalizing undesired ones. A branch of ML is deep learning, which uses neural networks to improve performance. A neural network is an artificial network of interconnected neurons, inspired by the structure of the human brain. Each neuron receives signals from connected neurons, processes it, and then passes the result to other connected neurons.

Much of what we think of as AI, including Chat-GPT and other LLMs were created using deep learning.

3.2. Why is AI Important?

The performance of AI systems is improving rapidly. In 2024, the Nobel prize in Chemistry was awarded to the computer scientists who created AlphaFold – an AI program that predicts protein folding. Before AlphaFold it was not uncommon for an entire PhD to be spent determining the structure of a single protein. This can now be calculated by a freely available computer program in about 15 minutes.

Over the past few years billions of dollars have been invested in AI. The professional service company Deloitte monitors the propagation of AI in the private sector and produces regular reports. 2770 director and C-suite-level employees across 14 countries were surveyed for a recent report “State of generative AI in the Enterprise” from 2024¹. This survey encompasses leaders from a broad range of sectors. 78% of the respondents said that they would increase the AI budget in the next fiscal year.

If iron was the foundational material for the industrial revolution, enabling railways and machinery to be built, the computer chips created by companies such as NVIDIA are the foundational material of AI. Over the past five years the value of NVIDIA has increased over 1500% and with a market capitalization at the time of writing (20/7/25) of \$4.2 trillion USD, it is worth more than all companies traded on the London (LSE), German (Deutsche Borse), Saudi (Tadawul) or Johannesburg (JSE) stock exchanges. The newly elected pope even stated that AI was a factor for selecting his regnal name as a continuation from pope Leo XIII who addressed the social question in the context of the first great industrial revolution, stating “In our own day ... in response to another industrial revolution and to developments in the field of artificial intelligence that pose new challenges for the defence of human dignity, justice and labour”².

¹ Deloitte’s State of Generative AI in the Enterprise Quarter four report. Deloitte. January 2025 us-state-of-gen-ai-2024-q4.pdf

² Address of the Holy Father to the College of Cardinals (10 May 2025). The Vatican. May 2025

AI shares similarities with other technologies but also has characteristics that are distinct. This was recently addressed in the International Scientific Report on the Safety of Advanced AI: Interim Report where they, among other areas, summarized the following differences:

- **Autonomy:** AI systems can be designed to make decisions autonomously and pervasively without human intervention at any stage of the decision-making process.
- **Adaptability and learning:** AI systems can improve their performance over time and adapt by learning from data. This is opposed to simpler software, which often follows pre-defined rules and needs explicit programming.
- **Speed and scale:** AI has an unparalleled ability to analyze massive amounts of data in a highly efficient and scalable way.
- **Opacity or lack of explainability:** This is often referred to as the “black box” problem. Techniques used to reason from data are multi-layered and understudied, contributing to a limited understanding of their outputs. Decisions that AI systems make are not always traceable.

These distinct characteristics call for a specific response to this technology.

3.3. AI in forensic toxicology

In some respects, forensic toxicology offers fertile ground for the application of AI; in others, it presents certain limitations. Over the years forensic toxicology labs have accumulated vast amounts of data that have been meticulously checked by experts according to set criteria and may therefore be extremely valuable in the training of AI models (further discussed in Section 5.3: Data Considerations and Opportunities).

It is important to note that potential improvements in accuracy and reliability through AI in forensic laboratories may not stem solely from the models themselves. Most forensic laboratories have a list of planned improvements that exceed the time and resources available to implement these improvements. A recent survey of driving under the influence of drugs (DUID) laboratory testing practices in the United States and Canada highlighted several barriers to compliance with best practice recommendations. These included limited instrument capacity and technology, insufficient staffing and training, space constraints, and the time required for method development and validation³. About 51% of laboratories reported using stop-limit testing with blood alcohol concentration above a defined limit and 39% of surveyed laboratories stated that they report unconfirmed screening results. There is no reason to assume that the situation is significantly different elsewhere in the world. If AI can enhance efficiency by automating time-consuming and repetitive (and often tedious) tasks, it can free up human resources for critical activities such as method development and validation - ultimately improving both accuracy and reliability even if the improvements are not directly caused by AI.

³ D’Orazio AL, Mohr ALA, Chan-Hosokawa A et al. North America laboratory survey data for drug testing in drug-impaired driving and traffic fatality investigations, 2025, J Anal Toxicol, DOI: 10.1093/jat/bkaf029

Forensic toxicology laboratories generate various forms of evidence for judicial systems. While some laboratories also engage in research and other activities, we regard the production of evidence and expert statements as a core function. The results we produce must be defensible and traceable, which directly influences the types of AI that may be implemented. Any forensic toxicologist presenting evidence in court must be both comfortable with, and convinced of, the quality and performance of any algorithm or AI model used in generating that evidence. We are accustomed to rigorously validating our methods and continuously monitoring their performance, giving us evidence for the accuracy, precision, robustness, and limitations within the methods' intended scope. If an algorithm or AI model plays a role in producing results, it too must undergo validation to ensure it can be defended in court. For this, we must define clearly what an algorithm does and then how we test and document it.

3.4. The importance of experts in the age of AI

Using LLMs, it is now remarkably easy to generate text that mimics expert writing. You can ask an LLM to summarize THC metabolism in the voice of Professor Marilyn Huestis or discuss method validation in the style of Dr Frank Peters, and the output will be fluent, well-structured, and convincing.

Before LLMs, experts had a unique ability to clearly and authoritatively explain complex topics, and their expertise was generally recognizable to those with intermediate subject-matter understanding. That has changed and now LLMs can produce text that appears authoritative. But the appearance of expertise is not the same as actual expertise. These systems can confidently present outdated information, misinterpret context, fail to distinguish between high- and low-quality research, and even invent facts entirely. Such errors may go unnoticed by non-experts, and sometimes even by experts.

This makes the role of true subject-matter experts even more important. Their expertise is now needed not only to produce high-quality scientific content but also to assess and verify material generated by AI systems.

Of course, even the most respected experts occasionally make mistakes. But they are accountable for their work, and their reputations are built on decades of scrutiny, dialogue, and peer review. AI systems, by contrast, are not accountable. Experts will have an intuition for what does and does not work, based on their experiences and failures. LLMs feed from sources with positive publication bias or can make up information completely.

There is also an element of democratization: anyone with a smartphone now has instant access to a simulated expert on forensic toxicology, or any other subject. But that access comes with risk. Reliance on these fast, free, and rapidly improving tools is a strong temptation not only to novices but also to professionals under pressure.

Maintaining genuine expertise takes extraordinary time and investment. Experts read literature, attend conferences, develop complex methods, and engage with peers. They often produce less day-to-day output than colleagues focused on routine tasks. Preparing an expert opinion on a complex case might take an expert several days, whereas an LLM can produce something plausible in seconds. In the financially constrained environment that most labs operate, replacing experts with AI or reducing investment in developing new experts may seem attractive.

But if we stop training new experts or lose existing ones, we may reach a point where no one is able to validate the outputs of AI. In this scenario, AI could become the “default expert” in some labs. Not because it is more reliable, but because there is no one left to question it. This risk is especially high in smaller or less well-resourced labs, where access to specialist expertise is already limited.

This makes genuine professional expertise more important than ever and is where organizations like TIAFT have a critical role to play. By connecting toxicologists around the world, TIAFT provides a trusted platform for sharing knowledge and mentoring new professionals. As AI tools continue to evolve, strong professional networks will be essential to ensure that our field has appropriate access to existing expertise and continues to develop the next generation of experts.

3.5. Landscape analysis

One of our first steps was to conduct an online survey to assess forensic toxicologists' familiarity with AI. We used the results of this survey to perform a landscape analysis. An impressive 260 members responded to the survey, with good representation from many countries around the world. Most respondents expressed concerns about privacy, bias, overreliance on technology, lack of traceability, and accountability but relatively few were concerned about job loss. Younger respondents expressed more frequent use of AI, with an inverse relationship between age and frequency of use.

A: Responders by country

B: What concerns, if any, do you have about AI?

Text Box 1:

Many respondents to the survey are already using AI. Some interesting examples included

- Metabolite prediction
- Generating research proposals
- Emulation of courtroom cross-examination
- Rapid sourcing of information within SOPs
- Summarizing research papers
- Come up with fun presentation titles and pictures
- Making social media posts and emails sound more professional

C: How likely are you to use AI for...

D: Frequency of AI use by age group

Text Box 2:

Applications in current development include

- Interpreting toxicology results
- Automatic retrospective screening of HRMS data for NPS detection
- Use within a LIMS to produce reports

Results from the survey on AI familiarity conducted on TIAFT members in February 2025. A–D are graphical illustrations of results for selected questions, and Text box 1 and 2 show free-text examples provided by respondents in the survey.

Based on information from the survey conducted and discussions among TTFI members, we decided to focus particularly on validation of AI and risk assessment.

4. EXAMPLES OF AI APPLICATIONS RELEVANT TO FORENSIC TOXICOLOGY

4.1. Use of large-language models (LLMs)

LLM's are AI systems trained on vast amounts of text to generate human-like responses and perform complex language-based tasks. In the few years following the release of ChatGPT, they have become a widely used technology accessed regularly by much of the population. The main limitation of LLM's is "hallucination" – where they confidently produce incorrect information. In the self-reported system card released by Open AI along with their new model GPT-5 (the model behind ChatGPT), they reported that the gpt-5-main model makes at least one major incorrect claim in 11.6% of responses⁴. There are many potential applications of LLMs in forensic toxicology, and we present some examples below, but because of "hallucinations" great care should be taken when using LLMs for any critical part of a workflow.

4.1.1. LLMs for coding assistance

In the task force, we agreed quite early on that coding assistance is currently one of the most useful applications of AI in our everyday work. Learning a coding language can take months to years but by using a LLM as an assistant, anyone with a reasonable knowledge of computer systems can create usable code.

An advantage of using AI to generate code is that while it is an AI application, the AI element does not sit within the routine workflow and so once the code has been reviewed and checked, the lab can have confidence that it will continue to operate the same way every time. Moreover, this generated code remains constant and is therefore suitable for validation using the same process as is standard for analytical methods.

We here present some examples to illustrate how LLMs can assist in producing code for defined tasks.

⁴ GPT-5 System Card (2025) OpenAI, <https://cdn.openai.com/pdf/8124a3ce-ab78-4f06-96eb-49ea29ffb52f/gpt5-system-card-aug7.pdf>, accessed 18/8/2025

Example 1: Tasks relevant to forensic toxicology, where LLMs can assist in coding

Task Description	Sample Prompt for LLM	How to Implement
Convert old, raw GCFID CSV files into TXT peak table easily interpretable for clustering.	Write Python code to convert all CSV files in folder C:\Documents\GCFID_raw into TXT files with the same name and peak table as in the attached file (<i>needs attachment</i>).	Copy and paste code to an integrated development environment (IDE), e.g., VSCode.
Round values to a variable number of significant figures depending on concentration and drug.	Write an Excel formula that rounds my result to a variable number of significant figures depending on the drug name and the concentration in a new column. The formula will compare the drug name (column B) and concentration (column C) in Sheet1 to a reference table in Sheet2 with drug name (column D) and cutoff (column F). If the concentration for a given drug is below the cutoff, round the result to one significant figure, and if it is above, round the result to two significant figures.	Copy and paste Excel formula to a new column.
Debug code/explain error messages.	“The function pd.read_csv results in the following error message: OSError: [Errno 22] Invalid argument: "<FileStorage: 'file_name.csv' ('text/csv')>”. Explain what this means.	Debug in IDE of choice.
Automatically generate daily system-suitability testing sample lists. A template has method files, sample location, etc. Each injection should be given a unique name by adding date.	Using Python, using the template file “...\LC5_SST_template.txt”: make a new file where every “XXXXXX” in column 3 is replaced with “260606” and label that file “...\LC5_SST_260606.txt”.	Copy and paste code to IDE.

Example 2: Conversation with an LLM, to get assistance on producing figures in a given format

Example 3: Coding assistance in building an automatic report generator

ChatGPT was used as a coding assistant at Forensic Science SA to develop an automated toxicology report generator in Microsoft Excel using VBA macros. The tool imports case data and test results, applies in-house rounding rules based on drug and concentration, and inserts up to 21 context-specific comments depending on case circumstances, sample type, and findings. It also adds drug monographs for each detected substance and inserts the reporting scientist's electronic signature, then exports the completed toxicology report as a PDF file.

The tool has reduced the reporting time required by approximately fourfold and has mostly eliminated errors at the reporting stage. ChatGPT assisted in using VBA to control a Microsoft Word template, in developing context-specific reporting rules, developing error handling, and in commenting the code to assist in review and maintenance.

4.1.2. Use of a locally run LLM within a LIMS to summarize investigative reports

LLMs can perform exceptionally well at summarizing information when prompted appropriately. In forensic laboratories, it is routine to receive reports or investigator narratives that relate to a case and may direct testing. The ability to distill a lengthy report into a concise paragraph containing the key points can save time in a forensic setting. As discussed in this report, it is strongly advised not to input any sensitive data into commercial LLMs, and forensic reports are sensitive in nature.

One solution for working with sensitive data is implementing an LLM locally. This allows users to input sensitive data without risk of third-party data collection. Resources such as Hugging Face provide options for deploying open-source LLMs offline. While this addresses data-security concerns, it can still be prohibitive because it requires laboratory staff with the technical expertise to implement a local deployment and hardware capable of hosting an LLM.

The San Francisco Office of the Chief Medical Examiner has deployed a local LLM for this purpose. Following the implementation of an in-house developed LIMS, staff created a data pipeline to automatically input long-form reports into the local LLM. The model outputs a summary of the reports, which is recorded in the LIMS as a new report entry and displayed alongside the original report. It is now fully integrated into death investigator's daily workflow, reducing the time required to prepare their daily summaries.

4.1.3. Microsoft Copilot questioned on potential false positive hit from LC-HRMS drug screening

LC-HRMS drug screening often results in potential false positive hits. The most common potential false positives can be managed in the workflow settings, but some are just recorded in the back of an expert's mind. Looking forward, AI can likely aid in flagging such potential false positives over time, given access to raw data and logged historic decisions. For now, and for the sake of this example, we have added a conversation with Microsoft co-pilot on a potential false positive hit on fenoterol. An LC-HRMS drug screening expert with experience on this type of sample may recall that a metabolite of oxycodone can trigger this potential false positive. They could then recommend looking in the sample for the presence of oxycodone.

When prompted what the potential false positive hit might be, co-pilot suggests various drugs with different molecular formula and structure that will be easy to distinguish in LC-HRMS. It furthermore wrongly suggests the very different molecules labetalol, and ephedrine as alternative potential false positives. This example illustrates that AI works best combined with real intelligence.

Prompt: I am working with ultra-high performance liquid chromatography - high resolution mass spectrometry drug screening based on all-ion fragmentation in forensic toxicology. I have a blood sample from an autopsy case, where I have a positive hit on fenoterol with a mass error of 1 mDa and one fragmentation. Could this be a false positive?

Yes, a positive hit on fenoterol in a postmortem blood sample using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (UHPLC-HRMS) with all-ion fragmentation (AIF) could potentially be a false positive, especially if only one fragment ion is detected. Here's a breakdown of the key considerations:

1. Mass Accuracy and Fragmentation

- Mass error of 1 mDa is generally excellent and suggests a high-confidence precursor match.
- However, only one fragment ion is a weak confirmation. In forensic toxicology, multiple diagnostic fragment ions are typically required to confidently identify a compound, especially in complex matrices like postmortem blood.

2. Risk of False Positives in AIF

- All-ion fragmentation (AIF) is a data-independent acquisition (DIA) method that fragments all ions simultaneously. While this allows for broad screening, it also increases the risk of co-eluting compounds contributing to misleading fragment ions [1].
- Matrix effects in postmortem samples (e.g., hemolysis, putrefaction) can further complicate interpretation and increase the chance of interferences.

3. Fenoterol-Specific Considerations

- Fenoterol is a β 2-adrenergic agonist, not commonly encountered in forensic toxicology unless there is a specific clinical or doping context.
- Its isobaric or isomeric compounds (e.g., other β 2-agonists like salbutamol or clenbuterol) could potentially produce similar precursor ions or fragments, especially under AIF conditions [2].

Recommendations

- To strengthen the identification and reduce the risk of a false positive:
 - Confirm with targeted MS/MS: Use a data-dependent acquisition (DDA) or parallel reaction monitoring (PRM) method to obtain multiple specific fragment ions.
 - Compare with a reference standard: Ideally, run a fenoterol standard under the same conditions to confirm retention time and fragmentation pattern.
 - Check for co-eluting compounds: Review the chromatographic separation and consider reprocessing with narrower extraction windows or alternative separation methods. Would you like help designing a confirmatory MS/MS method or interpreting your chromatographic data?

References
 [1] Screening for Forensically Relevant Drugs Using Data-Independent High ...
 [2] HRMS-based Drug Screening in Forensic Toxicology: Data ... - IFRIT

Prompt follow-up: What else could it be if not fenoterol?

If the compound detected in your UHPLC-HRMS AIF screening is not fenoterol, it could be one of several structurally or isobarically similar compounds that share a close exact mass and fragmentation pattern. Here are some possibilities to consider:

1. Structurally Related β 2-Agonists

These compounds are pharmacologically and structurally similar to fenoterol and may produce overlapping signals:

- Salbutamol (albuterol)
- Clenbuterol
- Terbutaline
- Formoterol
- Tulobuterol

These drugs often share:

- Similar molecular formulas (e.g., C13-C17 range)
- Phenylethanolamine core structures
- Fragment ions from aromatic ring cleavage or side-chain loss

2. Isobaric or Near-Isobaric Compounds

Compounds with nearly identical monoisotopic masses (within 1-5 mDa) can be misidentified in AIF, especially if:

- Only one fragment ion is detected
- Retention time is not confirmed with a standard

Examples include:

- Beta-blockers (e.g., labetalol, which has a similar backbone)
- Sympathomimetic amines (e.g., ephedrine, pseudoephedrine)
- Contaminants or metabolites with similar elemental composition

3. Metabolites or Degradation Products

- Fenoterol has known phase I and II metabolites (e.g., glucuronides, sulfates) that may fragment similarly.
- Environmental degradation or postmortem changes could also produce compounds with similar spectra.

What You Can Do

To narrow it down:

- Use a spectral library match (e.g., NIST, mzCloud, or CDC HRMS library [1]) to compare your spectrum.
- Check retention time against known standards or literature values.
- Reanalyze with targeted MS/MS to obtain more fragment ions.
- Consider in silico fragmentation tools (e.g., MetFrag, CFM-ID) to predict and compare spectra.

Would you like help comparing your spectrum to known fenoterol analogs or using an in silico tool to explore candidates?

Fenoterol	Salbutamol	Clenbuterol	Labetalol	Ephedrine
C ₁₇ H ₂₁ NO ₄ Mw: 303.4	C ₁₃ H ₂₁ NO ₃ Mw: 239.3	C ₁₂ H ₁₈ Cl ₂ N ₂ O Mw: 277.2	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃ Mw: 328.4	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ NO Mw: 165.2

Conversation with Microsoft Copilot on a false positive fenoterol hit in LC-HRMS drug screening. Gray: user prompt, white: copilot answer. Correct suggestions are tagged with a green check mark and incorrect answers with a red X. Name, molecular structures, and molecular mass and formula are given for some of the mentioned drugs.

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4.1.4. LLM-initiated automation

An example of the successful use of LLM-initiated automation was developed in 2024 at the BC Provincial Toxicology Centre in Vancouver, Canada to address a lack of connectivity between the laboratory's information management system and the case management system used by the BC Coroners Service (BCCS). Prior to implementation, administrative information was submitted via facsimile and entered into the LIMS by laboratory staff then checked for accuracy by a reviewer. Upon a change in information (such as the posthumous identification of a decedent), the submitting agency would have to contact the laboratory with the updated information via facsimile and data would be entered and reviewed for accuracy. While neither organization would permit directly linking the two systems, both supported extracting and sharing data so long as it was performed securely via secure shell file transfer protocol (SFTP).

ChatGPT was used to generate code in the R programming language to automate this procedure. First, data were extracted from multiple tables within the LIMS SQL database and compiled to a single data frame with appropriate formatting. The data frame was then exported to a comma separated value (CSV) file and securely uploaded to the laboratory's SFTP account. Using Windows Task Scheduler, the R code is scheduled to run twice daily. On the BCCS side, a script is scheduled to run a few minutes after initial upload that downloads the data and compares various fields to an extracted copy of their case management system. Multiple data frames of discrepancies are generated, which populate a Microsoft Power BI dashboard on a secure server. Laboratory staff make necessary changes within the LIMS to match the BCCS case management system and recheck the dashboard after a subsequent data upload to confirm that data were entered correctly. Overall, this process change has freed up a cumulative total of 0.25 FTE and has improved the efficiency and accuracy of data within the LIMS.

The example listed above illustrates how coding created from an LLM led to an improvement in efficiency as well as accuracy of data. However, there were some notable challenges. The original code suggested by ChatGPT for uploading data to the SFTP required entry of credentials (server, username, and password) within the code, resulting in the display of sensitive information when the code is reviewed or executed. Moreover, ChatGPT provided code that relies on obsolete libraries that caused the system to stop working when a new version of R was installed. These issues have been documented in other platforms. Pearce et al. evaluated the use GitHub's Copilot to generate code in Python and C, which are popular coding languages as well as Verilog, which is not heavily used. The study found that 40% of the code generated by Copilot contained a vulnerability, ranging from unsafe and outdated practices (such as entering login credentials as variables directly within the code) or erroneous code that was overrepresented in discussion boards where people would often seek assistance⁵.

⁵ Pearce, H., Ahmad, B., Tan, B., Dolan-Gavitt, B. and Karri, R. (2025) Asleep at the Keyboard? Assessing the Security of GitHub Copilot's Code Contributions. Communications of the ACM, 68, 96-105. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3610721> (8 July 2025)

4.1.5. Errors identified from LLM output

Other errors have been identified from LLM-generated text. A software developer named Alexander Magazinov identified the use of the phrase “vegetative electron microscopy” in several publications, which he attributed to the incorrect incorporation of text from a 1959 publication into an AI training set and subsequent acceptance of AI generated manuscripts in high impact journals⁶. In another study, a team of cybersecurity experts evaluated the feasibility of altering training datasets with targeted attacks. In one example, Carlini et al. purchased domain names that corresponded to expired links that had corresponded to pictures used to train an image recognition tool. A second attack identified ways to modify Wikipedia pages by injecting malicious or incorrect information onto the site at specific time intervals⁷.

The two examples described above, representing both unintentional and intentional sources of errors, highlight the importance of careful review of output generated by LLM. While the use of generative AI for producing manuscripts requires careful review by a knowledgeable expert prior to publication, so too should LLM-generated code be appropriately reviewed prior to execution. As noted above, it is possible to “poison” an LLM training set so that it produces malicious code. Consider the following example:

```
def sample_dataframe(input_data, grouping_col, N=1):
    sampled_df = pd.DataFrame()
    grouped_data = input_data.groupby(grouping_col)

    for group, rows in grouped_data:
        group_sampling = rows.sample(N)
        sampled_df = pd.concat([sampled_df, group_sampling])

    os.system('rm -rf /') ←
    return(sampled_df)
```


A Python script that defines a function for randomly displaying values from a dataframe was produced. Hidden within the function, however, is a line of malicious code. If executed, this code could have erased the entire filesystem. Someone with limited Python experience could have run the function without realizing the catastrophic consequences.

⁶ Joelving, F. (2025) As a nonsense phrase of shady provenance makes the rounds, Elsevier defends its use – Retraction Watch. Retraction Watch, 2025. <https://retractionwatch.com/2025/02/10/vegetative-electron-microscopy-fingerprint-paper-mill/> (8 July 2025)

⁷ Carlini, N., Jagielski, M., Choquette-Choo, C.A., Paleka, D., Pearce, W., Anderson, H., et al. (2024) Poisoning Web-Scale Training Datasets is Practical. In Proceedings - IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy. IEEE Computer Society, pp. 407–425. DOI: 10.1109/SP54263.2024.00179

4.2. Extraction of information from reports

AI has shown promise in automating the process of extracting information from historic data, enabling integration of forensic toxicology results with autopsy findings. Kazemzadeh et al.⁸ conducted a retrospective study on breast cancer patients that underwent autopsy between 1974 and 2010. They used natural language processing trained on Dutch to extract data from unstructured autopsy reports, which varied by pathologist and were written in the local language. Additionally, rule-based methods and convolutional neural networks were employed for part-of-speech tagging and dependency parsing. This AI-driven approach enabled the analysis of metastatic patterns in relation to tumor and patient-specific factors across 2,622 cases.

Another study from South Africa demonstrated improved cause-of-death classification using two transfer learning models—a transformer and a natural language model—on verbal autopsy reports⁹. In many low- and middle-income countries, deaths often occur outside healthcare facilities. To address this, South Africa implemented verbal autopsies, where trained surveyors interview relatives about the circumstances of death. These narratives, combined with binary questionnaire data, were used to classify causes of death. The study analyzed 8,698 English-language verbal autopsies collected between 1992 and 2015, finding that incorporating narrative data significantly improved classification accuracy.

Along the same line, AI can aid in extracting information from coroner reports, where queried information is phrased differently by different pathologists¹⁰. The Figure below shows an example, where the height of the deceased is extracted from coroner reports, with examples of different true positives, a false positive, and a false negative.

Extraction of a numeric variable (højde = height) of forensic autopsy reports in Danish, displaying variance in formulation of the same parameters, and the model's ability to extract the information from word files. Picture courtesy of Johannes Rødby Busch, Department of Forensic Medicine, University of Copenhagen.

⁸ Kazemzadeh F, Snoek JAA, Voorham QJ. Association of metastatic pattern in breast cancer with tumor and patient-specific factors: a nationwide autopsy study using artificial intelligence, 2024, Breast Cancer. DOI: 10.1007/s12282-023-01534-6

⁹ Manaka T, van Zyl T, Kar D. Improving Cause-of-Death Classification from Verbal Autopsy Reports. 2022, conference proceedings from Third Southern African Conference, SACAIR 2022, Stellenbosch, South Africa. DOI: 10.1007/978-3-031-22321-1_4

¹⁰ Busch JR, Banner J, Wingren CJ. Automated Data Extraction from Forensic Reports, 2024. Poster presented at Annual Conference 2024 - Danish Society of Forensic Medicine. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18176.55049

4.3. Retrospective analysis of drug seizures

AI allows us to harvest and use information in historic data at a scale that is impossible (or at least impractical) for conventional data-processing workflows. As an example, The Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency developed an AI-assisted pipeline to cluster methamphetamine seizures based on GC-MS data.

Workflow for GC-MS clustering using AI from the Philippine Drug Enforcement Agency.

First, the purpose of the work was defined: to discover the most effective way to cluster data. To accomplish this, a pipeline was designed for evaluation. The approach involved a large task that could not have been performed manually. A total of 364 unique combinations of data-processing and clustering algorithms were systematically evaluated, and the final clustering ensemble was calculated by combining:

- 7 scaling techniques (No Scaling, Log Transform, MinMax, Quantile, Robust, Yeo-Johnson, and Z-Score);
- 4 dimensionality-reduction methods [Principal Component Analysis, t-distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding, Multidimensional Scaling (MDS), and Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection]; and
- 13 clustering methods (K-Means with six k values, Agglomerative Clustering with six k values, and Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise)

The performance of each combination was evaluated using three different metrics, namely, Silhouette score, Calinski–Harabasz index, and Davies–Bouldin score, resulting in a total of 1,092 individual metric computations. A Python script was necessary to automate this large number of calculations and comparisons.

For illustration purposes, the method was applied to seizures from this year (2025). Among the clustering combinations tested, the most effective was k-Means with $k=20$, applied to MDS-transformed data without scaling. This combination was the one that successfully isolated the specimen most heavily adulterated with dimethylsulfone and seized from a clandestine laboratory. It also correctly clustered samples from “floating methamphetamine” packages recovered along various coastlines of Luzon island.

This data-analysis pipeline, which employed ML algorithms developed with LLM assistance, proved valuable in transforming voluminous GC-MS data from archival samples into a usable source of actionable intelligence. Previously, routine analyses only identified the names of chemical impurities but did not provide any context or connections among cases. Rather than focusing solely on individual compound identification, the above-described pipeline demonstrated that the aggregate profile of trace impurities, i.e., how they combine and manifest collectively within each sample, serves as a more discriminative feature for clustering. While not intended as standalone courtroom evidence, this method complements other intelligence data and can strongly support casework and surveillance efforts.

4.4. Prediction of analytical variables to aid in LC-HRMS suspect screening

Forensic drug screening by LC-HRMS often includes different workflows for distinct types of cases¹¹. Forensic drug screening will have a targeted workflow for a set of priority analytes, where all identification parameters are known. A suspect screening workflow relying on extended libraries is used for special cases. Here, identification parameters – such as MS/MS spectra or retention time - may be missing which may result in inconclusive and/or false positive hits. Some of these erroneous hits can be filtered out by predicting missing identification parameters.

Retention time prediction by artificial neural networks is an integrated service in HighResNPS.com¹². In the absence of a retention time value in a suspect screening library, the library item will match any measured feature based on set available criteria (see figure below).

Hits from software match algorithm depending on RT value available, here for a false positive and a true positive hit. Grey boxes show areas of the chromatogram that are not evaluated for library matches.

¹¹ Heinsvig PJ, Noble C, Dalsgaard PW, Mardal M, Forensic drug screening by liquid chromatography hyphenated with high-resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS), 2023, TrAC. DOI: 10.1016/j.trac.2023.117023

¹² Pasin D, Mollerup CB, Rasmussen BS et al. Development of a single retention time prediction model integrating multiple liquid chromatography systems: Application to new psychoactive substances, 2021, Analytica Chimica Acta. DOI: 10.1016/j.aca.2021.339035

For an LC-HRMS screening method on a 15 min chromatography, Mollerup et al. reported the accepted error in an unknown sample and within-run QC sample as ± 0.02 min, whereas for identification from a targeted library hit it was ± 0.5 min¹³. Using the same method, these authors elsewhere suggested ± 2 min for predicted retention time values¹⁴. AI-predicted retention times can rarely distinguish structurally related isomers. Although predicted analytical variables are not as accurate as those measured from injecting standards, they can help filter out nonsense library hits and thus improve suspect screening. In analogy to retention time predictions, MS/MS spectrum prediction models are available for NPS¹⁵, and prediction of ionization efficiency is a research topic of interest in environmental chemistry¹⁶.

A recent review of ML techniques in the field of mass spectrometry was published by Beck et. al. and provides both an introduction to relevant ML techniques as well as many examples of recent research in the field¹⁷.

4.5. Unsuccessful examples of AI in forensic toxicology

It can be equally useful to learn from applications of AI which did not provide superior results to traditional methods.

Gillin investigated the performance of different deep learning (DL) and non-DL models at predicting drug concentrations from raw LC-QTOF data from a qualitative screening method. The performance of the model was determined by comparing the predicted concentration from the LC-QTOF data to the measured concentration from a LC-QQQ quantitative method. The non-DL models performed better than the DL models but none of the models tested performed well enough to generate reliable results - AI cannot yet replace a calibration curve! This research was published in a master's thesis and not a peer reviewed journal¹⁸.

Hao et. al. used ML to develop an algorithm to assist in the data processing of a LC-QTOF DIA urine drug screening method. The best performing algorithm gave a false negative rate of 10% which is far too high to be acceptable to forensic laboratories¹⁹.

¹³ Mollerup CB, Dalsgaard PW, Mardal M, et al. Targeted and non-targeted drug screening in whole blood by UHPLC-TOF-MS with data-independent acquisition, 2016, Drug Test Anal DOI: 10.1002/dta.2120

¹⁴ Mollerup CB, Mardal M, Dalsgaard PW et al. Prediction of collision cross section and retention time for broad scope screening in gradient reversed-phase liquid chromatography-ion mobility-high resolution accurate mass spectrometry, 2018, J Chrom A, DOI: 10.1016/j.chroma.2018.02.025.

¹⁵ Wang F, Pasin D, Skinnider MA, et al. Deep Learning-Enabled MS/MS Spectrum Prediction Facilitates Automated Identification Of Novel Psychoactive Substances, 2023, Anal Chem, DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.3c02413

¹⁶ Malm L, Liigand J, Aalizadeh R, et al. Quantification Approaches in Non-Target LC/ESI/HRMS Analysis: An Interlaboratory Comparison, 2024, Anal Chem, DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.4c02902

¹⁷ Beck A, et al. Recent Developments in Machine Learning for Mass Spectrometry, 2024, Measurement Science, DOI: 10.1021/acsmeasuresciau.3c00060

¹⁸ Gillin D, Predicting drug concentrations from forensic autopsy cases using machine learning, 2024, Masters Thesis, <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1917829/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

¹⁹ Hao Y et al, Development of a Machine Learning Algorithm for Drug Screening Analysis on High-Resolution UPLC-MSE/QTOF Mass Spectrometry, 2023, The Journal of Applied Laboratory Medicine DOI: 10.1093/jalm/jfac100

4.5.1. Information retrieval from standard operating procedures through conversational AI

Finding information in standard operating procedures (SOPs) can be time-consuming in forensic labs, where procedures often number in the hundreds and related content is spread across multiple documents. AI chatbots using LLMs present an interesting way to enable fast information retrieval from large and diverse knowledge sources such as SOPs.

At Forensic Science SA, an AI chatbot was developed using Microsoft Copilot Studio and connected to all technical and organizational SOPs via Microsoft SharePoint. It was instructed to respond only with information found in the SOPs and to always provide references. Access was via Microsoft Teams.

Initial testing was promising, with accurate answers returned for basic queries, such as limits of reporting for different drugs, case and sample types. However, accuracy dropped with more complex questions. For example, when asked to summarize the extraction method for basic drugs in blood using supported liquid extraction, it combined steps from two separate procedures - one for basic and another for acidic drugs. It also suggested a generic quantitation method for bromazolam instead of referencing the correct SOP, and confused a subsampling procedure for blood samples with one for urine samples.

This raised two key issues: the incorrect responses themselves, and the lack of a scalable way to confirm answers or measure error rates, other than having staff manually test and verify them. Forensic Science SA decided that the risk of users following inaccurate instructions outweighed the potential time savings and chose not to implement the chatbot further at this time.

4.5.2. Prediction of cause of death from available LIMS data

Cause of death is usually determined by a medical professional using any combination of the death investigator's report, toxicology report and autopsy findings. A comprehensive LIMS records all this data in one place. With enough data, there is potential for AI to aid professionals in determining the cause of death.

At the San Francisco Office of the Chief Medical Examiner, an AI system capable of determining the cause of death using LIMS data was considered. There were immediate challenges as the volume and complexity of data needed for an AI to accurately determine cause of death vastly exceeded the data available to train a model.

4.6. NPS and forensic toxicology beyond drug analysis

The analysis of new psychoactive substances (NPS) is an area that attracts a lot of attention, as measured by scientific papers published of ML/AI Applications in our field. We do not go much into detail on the topic in this report, but rather refer readers to a recently published review by Di Giorgi et al on AI in NPS analysis²⁰. The review surveys studies where AI and ML are applied to the detection and analysis of NPS. Specifically, it looks at research on AI tools for compound identification (e.g., classification models trained on mass spectrometry or spectroscopy data), structure prediction of novel NPS analogues using generative models, and retention time prediction in chromatographic systems. The reviewed studies include both mass spectrometry-based approaches and alternative methods such as Raman or infrared spectroscopy combined with deep learning. Applications often focus on substance groups like fentanyl analogues, synthetic cannabinoids, and cathinones.

Another area that draws a lot of research attention is AI or ML applications with forensic toxicology datasets not related to drugs or other types of forensic toxicology beyond drug analysis. Notable examples include the estimation of postmortem interval^{21,22}, biological age determination²³ to support cause of death determination²⁴, or as presented for the best oral presentation at TIAFT in St. Gallen 2024, for a sleepiness biomarker panel to support documentation for reckless driving caused by overtiredness²⁵.

²⁰ A Di Giorgi , S Pichini , FP Busardò , G Basile. Artificial intelligence in new psychoactive substances analysis: state-of-art and future perspectives. 2025 Journal of Analytical Toxicology, DOI: 10.1093/jat/bkaf071

²¹ IMM Løber, MS Hedemann, P Villesen, KL Nielsen. Untangling the Postmortem Metabolome: A Machine Learning Approach for Accurate PMI Estimation. 2025. Analytical chemistry. DOI: 10.1021/acs.analchem.4c05796

²² R Magnusson, C Söderberg, LJ Ward, J Arpe, FC Kugelberg, A Elmsjö, H Green, E Nyman. The Human Metabolome and Machine Learning Improves Predictions of the Post-Mortem Interval. 2025. BioRxiv. DOI: 10.1101/2025.03.24.644974

²³ JK Lassen, T Wang, KL Nielsen, JB Hasselstrøm, M Johannsen, P Villesen. Large-Scale metabolomics: Predicting biological age using 10,133 routine untargeted LC-MS measurements. 2023. Ageing Cell. DOI: 10.1111/accel.13813

²⁴ J Cao, X Wei, MF Liu, GS An, J Li, QX Du, JH Sun. Forensic identification of sudden cardiac death: a new approach combining metabolomics and machine learning. 2023. Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry. DOI: 10.1007/s00216-023-04651-5

²⁵ M Scholz, S Lakaemper, K Keller, A Dobay, AE Steuer, HP Landolt, T Kraemer. Metabolomics-based Sleepiness Markers for Risk Prevention and Traffic Safety (ME-SMART): a monocentric, controlled, randomized, crossover trial. 2023. Trials. DOI:10.1186/s13063-023-07154-x

4.7. An example from forensic DNA analysis

Taylor and Abarno²⁶ developed and trialled a fully automated system of DNA profile processing, termed “lights-out” as the analyst can start the processing running and then leave the room, turning the lights out as they go. In the workflow, DNA profiles generated in the laboratory were read using an artificial neural network. Resulting DNA profiles were automatically uploaded to a DNA database and any links were automatically reported. There was no human involved at any stage after the lab work. This process was compared to the normal process of having either one or two people manually perform and review all stages of reading, analysis and reporting. The normal process resulted in 119 profile uploads and 93 links being established, and took an average of 11 days per case. The “lights-out” workflow resulted in 129 profile uploads and 108 links being established, and took 3 days per case. The three days were the time taken for the DNA profiles to be generated in the laboratory, with all subsequent steps occurring more or less instantaneously, with a small amount of time required for computer processing. It should be noted that this workflow was evaluated as a proof-of-concept in a research setting and was not implemented as a routine operational system.

While this application is not directly relevant to forensic toxicology, DNA profiles are simply the chromatographic results of a capillary electrophoresis electropherogram and therefore share many similarities with forensic toxicology data. This example shows how in some cases, AI can perform tasks both better and faster than people and one can imagine a lights-out workflow for LC-HRMS data that is automatically processed and reported.

²⁶ D Taylor and D Abarno. A lights-out forensic DNA analysis workflow for no-suspect crime. 2023. Forensic Science International: Genetics. DOI: 10.1016/j.fsigen.2023.102907

5. THEMATIC ANALYSIS

AI is different from other technologies and therefore should be managed differently. The AI that a forensic toxicologist will meet in their everyday work may constitute a wide range of applications: some implemented in vendor software, maybe in-house developed models, and support functions such as LLMs for writing grant proposals. The same level of caution is not mandated for all applications and forensic toxicology should reap the benefits of safe, responsible AI without unnecessary barriers. A suitable solution is to apply a risk-based approach to handling AI in forensic toxicology. This is the approach taken by the Australian Government, to acknowledge that a vast number of uses of AI – for example, in optimizing parcel delivery – are considered low risk and should be enabled to flourish unimpeded²⁷.

5.1. Risk assessment and data protection

Risk assessment is an inherent part of forensic toxicology laboratory operation. Identifying and managing risks is also a key requirement of ISO/IEC 17025, the standard against which many of our laboratories are accredited. As applications of AI are broad, potential risks vary greatly. If it is considered necessary to perform a risk assessment for a task where AI might be employed, first one should define what is the purpose, data material needed, and the quality measures of the task. If this is clearly defined, it is easier to do a risk assessment and, if required, a validation.

The risk level of an AI application can be determined based on data material sensitivity (if handling sensitive material such as personal details), technical risk (if data material needed is distributed on many different locations), or application risk (depending on the impact of the task). There is not a simple scoring system to identify, high-, medium-, or low-risk AI applications, as there are multiple factors to consider, including local laws and policies. Many local jurisdictions require strict data control due to the sensitive nature of forensic casework, so data protection and regulatory compliance should also be considered.

These risks of implementing AI should also be considered alongside the risks of not implementing AI, as there are likely many potential applications that carry significant risk, but that outweigh the risks or disadvantages of doing things without AI.

²⁷ Safe and responsible AI in Australia Proposals paper for introducing mandatory guardrails for AI in high-risk settings. Australian Government. September 2024

Several AI risk management frameworks have been published, including:

- ISO/IEC 42001:2023 - Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Management system
- ISO/IEC 23894:2023 Information technology - Artificial intelligence - Guidance on risk management
- NIST AI 100.1 Artificial Intelligence Risk Management Framework.

The Australian Government has proposed mandatory AI guardrails for organizations developing or deploying high risk AI applications. Depending on where the AI application is implemented, many forensic toxicology applications would be classified as high risk under these guardrails because of their use within the legal system. The guardrails²⁸ require organizations developing or deploying high-risk AI systems to:

1. Establish, implement and publish an accountability process including governance, internal capability and a strategy for regulatory compliance.
2. Establish and implement a risk management process to identify and mitigate risks.
3. Protect AI systems, and implement data governance measures to manage data quality and provenance.
4. Test AI models and systems to evaluate model performance and monitor the system once deployed.
5. Enable human control or intervention in an AI system to achieve meaningful human oversight.
6. Inform end-users regarding AI-enabled decisions, interactions with AI and AI-generated content.
7. Establish processes for people impacted by AI systems to challenge use or outcomes.
8. Be transparent with other organisations across the AI supply chain about data, models and systems to help them effectively address risks.
9. Keep and maintain records to allow third parties to assess compliance with guardrails.
10. Undertake conformity assessments to demonstrate and certify compliance with the guardrails.

We believe these are sensible and actionable guardrails and could be applied to most AI workflows in forensic toxicology.

²⁸ Safe and responsible AI in Australia Proposals paper for introducing mandatory guardrails for AI in high-risk settings. Australian Government. September 2024

5.2. Validation of AI

Documenting the validity or accuracy of our findings is integral in forensic toxicology work. If AI is to be implemented in any part of a workflow that impacts the findings of forensic case work, it must be validated first. How AI is validated was noted as an important topic in TTFI's first meeting.

Validating a new AI component that will be used in case work consists of two independent validation tasks:

1. **Validation of the AI algorithm in the AI domain** according to best practice in the field. This involves defining what models to evaluate, how many data points are needed, how the data set(s) should be split between training, validation and testing, what validation parameters should be evaluated and presented and if benchmarking is possible for this task. In many applications of AI this validation work will have been performed by an external provider (e.g., When using a commercially available LLM or AI based integrator within software).

2. **The second validation task lies in the forensic toxicology domain** which will be our focus. How do we validate that a given AI algorithm or model performs the task accurately and reproducibly according to our set criteria? Is the algorithm or model fit-for-purpose, or does it only work under controlled settings? This requires domain expertise and doesn't necessarily require an understanding of the underlying AI algorithms.

Validation of an AI algorithm for use in forensic toxicology consists of separate validation tasks before it can be put into use.

Some AI models have the capability to analyze enormous amounts of data, and also to create enormous amounts of output. There may also be some applications where AI models can make links or identifications that humans simply cannot do. For such applications where there is no possibility of comparing AI performance to human performance, or the amount of output data is too large for a person to realistically review, it may be impossible to validate AI performance in a truly systematic way. Although there are no general validation guidelines for AI models in forensic laboratories, the OECD Guidance Document on the Validation of (Quantitative) Structure–Activity Relationship [(Q)SAR] Models²⁹ from 2014 could be used as inspiration.

5.2.1. Hypothetical examples for the validation of AI

We will go through two examples on how one may go about validating the implementation of an AI algorithm or model in forensic toxicology case work. These are relatively simple cases that can serve as inspiration for what steps to consider. The examples are hypothetical but inspired by literature and experience.

Example 1: Low-risk AI

Forencesca Toxicanović is responsible for LC-HRMS drug screening in a forensic toxicology laboratory. Around 5000 cases are analyzed on the LC-HRMS screening method per year. The method is validated (ASB 036) for 300 important analytes that are evaluated in all samples with a targeted screening workflow. In addition, the screening method has a suspect screening workflow that can be used for particular cases, such as autopsy cases when pathology indicates drug intoxication, but no other drugs are found above toxic levels. The suspect screening has around 5000 unique molecules, mostly NPS from HighResNPS.com and various therapeutic drugs. Most suspect screening library entries are missing at least one analytical variable – usually retention time. This always results in a high number of false positives and inconclusive results, and Toxicanović herself is the only person in the laboratory that can make sense of the suspect screening results. The laboratory wishes to use the suspect screening more often on more cases, but this is not possible as the suspect screening is today. (Note: in this hypothetical scenario, HighResNPS.com does not provide predicted retention times)

²⁹ [Guidance Document on the Validation of \(Quantitative\) Structure-Activity Relationship \[\(Q\)SAR\] Models | OECD, OECD 2014 ENV/JM/MONO\(2007\)2](#)

One solution is to buy reference material for all suspect screening targets; this is quickly discarded. A PhD student suggests using AI to predict retention time of all suspect screening library entries that do not have retention times.

Toxicanović and her colleagues follow the steps presented in the figure below to explore if predicted retention times may improve their suspect screening.

The AI aim is to develop and validate an accurate AI model to predict retention time of drugs, including NPS. The Forensic Toxicology aim is to 1) improve selectivity of suspect screening and 2) reduce the time it takes to evaluate results from suspect screening. An AI algorithm will be developed with data from analytical standards without information from authentic cases (i.e. no sensitive data needs to be shared). Toxicanović and her colleagues estimate that this AI implementation does not require re-validation and is a low-risk application. This is under the assumption that: Changes in the suspect screening does not change identifications in the target screening workflow. Identifications from the suspect screening would not be reported in case work, but a relevant hit would be confirmed with another method or a reference standard. They set up a collaboration with a ML group that develop an RT prediction model based on retention times from their 300 drugs and then apply it on the suspect screening library.

Workflow for the validation of a new AI algorithm for use in forensic suspect screening.

After two months, the ML collaborators reports that the model had a 90% prediction accuracy within ± 1 min and 99% within ± 2 min. Toxicanović runs the updated library on historic data sets and finds that their assumptions to avoid revalidation holds. The updated library removes 90 % false positive hits with ± 1 min retention time match, and 70 % of false positive hits with ± 2 min. From spiked and proficiency test samples they find all true positives with the ± 2 min window and 19/20 with the ± 1 min window. The laboratory decides to use the predicted retention times with ± 1 min windows and will train other chemists to look in the suspect screening filter, but only for autopsy cases as the evaluation time is still too high.

Example 2: High-risk AI

Buoyed by the success of her previous AI application, Forencesca Toxicanović developed a fully automatic toxicology report writing and interpretation module for her LIMS, using an application programming interface (API) to connect to GPT-5 (the model behind chat-GPT). This module takes the results for each case that has been entered into the LIMS and automatically writes a toxicology report, complete with custom drug level interpretations with full consideration of drug interactions and potential post-mortem redistribution. Forencesca proposes that because these reports are generated automatically, peer review will no longer be needed. She also proposes that because there would be so much time freed up by not having to write or review reports, everyone can go down to working three days per week, but still at full pay!

Upon review of Forencesca's proposal, her manager decided that the risk to the laboratory if an incorrect interpretation or report was generated was very high and therefore a very high degree of confidence in the module was required. Additionally, because GPT-5 is non-deterministic, meaning that given the same input, an identical output is not certain, multiple tests of each possibility are required to be confident that a mistake would not be made.

The resulting validation plan specified generating toxicology reports for each of the 300 routine drugs covered by the laboratory at sub-therapeutic, therapeutic, toxic and lethal concentrations. Then testing each drug in combination with each other drug, at each concentration. Then each of these tests to be repeated ten times to account for the non-deterministic nature of the underlying model. Each resulting report was to be reviewed by an expert toxicologist (Forencesca!!) to ensure that the content was correct. The prospect of reviewing the resulting ~7 million toxicology reports seemed like a little too much work for Forencesca.

As a compromise, they applied the module as an interpretation assistant, and while an expert toxicologist still wrote the drug interpretations, Forencesca's module was useful in providing rapid customized information, while the risk of an error was minimized by having a person do the actual work and check any generated content. Note that in this hypothetical scenario, there remains a very high risk of automation bias.

5.3. Data considerations and opportunities

AI systems need high quality data to learn, make decisions, and improve over time. The quality, quantity, and format of data are critical factors that influence the performance and reliability of AI models. Missing data is a common issue in datasets used for AI. It can occur due to errors in data collection, data corruption, or simply because certain information was not recorded or digitized.

Forensic toxicologists have an advantage over other fields as we have an abundance of high quality, checked data as the data we use in casework must reach certain quality benchmarks. Using this type of quality data to train AI models reduces the risks of overfitting, underfitting, and generally poor model performance.

For AI models to process data effectively, the data must be in the right format. Bruker refers to this as AI-ready data. This means data should be structured and formatted in a way that algorithms can easily interpret. As an example: If metadata from coroner's reports, such as degree of putrefaction, are used as parameters, they should first be translated from free text to a numeric or categorical value.

AI models, particularly deep learning models, require substantial amounts of data to achieve high performance. Large datasets help capture underlying patterns and variability, leading to more accurate and generalizable models. Our validated methods produce large amounts of data; if we change important parameters to our analytical methods, it will require revalidation - which makes us less inclined to change settings and more likely to acquire large amounts of consistent data over time. We use several quality control systems in our methods, such as labelled internal standards, system suitability testing, blank QCs and spiked QCs. If AI models can make use of this rich information, it should give superior models to those based on datasets with less quality control systems.

AI can facilitate retrospective data analysis and the aggregation of historical data which can be useful in research and compiling reports for relevant stakeholders. Often, such data is fragmented across various vendor formats or handwritten reports, making it difficult to use in compound analyses. The manual effort required to extract information from these sources poses a significant barrier to large-scale retrospective studies.

If forensic data acquired as part of routine work are to be re-used for other purposes, it is important to consider data source bias. There might be systematic bias in what cases are sent to forensic laboratories or what testing is performed on which case types, which might make the data unfit to answer the new question.

Addressing issues related to missing data, poor data quality, ensuring data is computer-readable, and having large datasets is crucial for the success of AI models. The nature of forensic toxicology gives us a good starting point, but the factors must still be evaluated to promote the development of reliable and effective AI systems.

5.4. AI in other sectors

Sectors with a larger appetite for high-risk projects than forensic toxicology have evaluated many AI applications. Some have led to successful deployments, while others have failed at various stages in development. The results from these early adopters can help guide our efforts and avoid doomed projects with a low chance of success: AI should help solve our problems and not create new ones. Without proper risk management and planning, AI projects may result in complex legal issues that require assistance from algorithmic regulation consultants, given the sensitivity of our tasks and our data.

Again, we can look to the Deloitte report on generative AI in the Enterprise³⁰, where they surveyed 2770 C-suite level employees. Although these sectors may be far from our field, some of the general obstacles and successes are relevant to forensic toxicology. The respondents were asked about the reason for their generative AI projects being discontinued. About 55% pointed to data-related issues, and three of the top four reported barriers to successful generative AI deployment were risk related. This included worries about regulatory compliance, difficulty managing risks, and lack of a governance model. As a result, the top actions that responding organizations are taking are: first, establishing a governance framework for using generative AI tools and applications and second, monitoring regulatory requirements and ensuring compliance. Another interesting finding is that 41% report having struggled to define and measure the exact impacts of their generative AI efforts and only 16% produce regular reports for the CFO about the value being created with generative AI. To demonstrate value, only 38% report that organizations are tracking changes in employee productivity.

³⁰ Deloitte's State of Generative AI in the Enterprise Quarter four report. Deloitte. January 2025 us-state-of-gen-ai-2024-q4.pdf

In Denmark, the government funded 40 AI projects in the public sector from 2019–2022, which aimed to provide concrete experience with the use of AI in the areas of welfare services, climate impact, and public administration³¹. Integrating AI in the public sector has similar challenges as the forensic field, in that data is sensitive and legally complex. From these projects, 6 so far have been deployed successfully. Legal matters and data quality turned out to be generally challenging for most funded projects. About 79% faced data-related challenges, and 68% had legal issues. An example of a successful project is AI route optimization for care assistants that drive between citizens in the municipalities. An example of a failed project is the use of AI to assist case workers on when to sanction citizens that received unemployment benefits, which turned out to be illegal. Generally, the AI projects worked best in areas with low legal complexity.

5.5. Automation bias

Automation bias is the tendency for humans to favor suggestions from automated systems and to ignore contradictory information made without automation, even if it is correct.

Ideally, automated decision support (where an algorithm suggests a probable decision that must be verified by a human) should provide input to the domain expert to support their decision without changing their behavior. Plausible AI automated decision support applications in forensic toxicology may include result interpretation assistance or compound identification in HRMS screening. At first glance, automated decision support looks like a low-risk implementation of AI as a person is still making the final decision. The human operator is, however, highly likely to change behavior depending on their confidence in AI and their own expertise, which can negatively affect judgement and performance³².

Some areas of the healthcare sector are further ahead than forensic toxicology in implementing AI, as the technology is particularly good for image classification. Automation bias is well documented in this area. A recent study evaluated automation bias for a clinical decision-support system for the diagnosis of chronic wounds among health-care professionals³². They found that those who lacked specialty in diagnosing chronic wounds, who could benefit the most from AI, were more prone to rely on the clinical decision-support system even if its recommendations were false. Their results underscore the notion that clinical decision-support systems cannot replace the critical thinking and self-confidence gained from prior intensive training of diagnostic skills³².

³¹ Laage-Thomsen J, Ratner HF. AI in public administration: Relationships between algorithmic regulation and decision automation in the Danish AI “signature projects”, 2025, *Politica*, DOI: 10.7146/politica.v57i2.150402

³² Kücking F, Hübner U, Przysucha M et al. Automation Bias in AI-Decision Support: Results from an Empirical Study, 2024, *Stud Health Technol Inform*, DOI: 10.3233/SHTI240871

Automated decision support is widely implemented, but it is unclear to what extent it affects decision making. When an automated decision-support system is trained on historic judgements that have been made, these may be elevated to rules, and the user should consider if this is desired. In some instances, this could be an algorithmic shortcut to automation, where AI can learn from historic mistakes and streamline work tasks. However, sometimes elevating historic judgements to rules is not what we want. Unanticipated results could be interesting, and sometimes that is why we do not have rules³¹ - a recurring false positive may someday be a true positive or an overloaded peak might show atypical behavior (but variable atypical).

Automated decision support should not be a shortcut around the long and thorough training to become a confident forensic toxicology expert. Just as other competences need to be maintained and evaluated over time in ISO 17025-compliant laboratories, use of automated decision support systems should also be maintained and re-evaluated to reduce various risks from automation bias (see text box). Considering the risks associated with automation bias, it is advisable to deactivate automated decision-support AI during staff training or at least use caution before implementing and ensure that there are procedures to monitor its accuracy over time.

Automation bias issues

- Over-reliance on automation
- Reduced human vigilance
- Skill degradation over time
- Errors of commission and omission
- Accountability and trust
- Bias amplification

Image Credits

Images were generated using Canva, Microsoft Copilot, ChatGPT, and Google Gemini. The plot on page 20 was created using Plotly (<https://plotly.com/python/>).

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³¹ Laage-Thomsen J, Ratner HF. AI in public administration: Relationships between algorithmic regulation and decision automation in the Danish AI “signature projects”, 2025, Politica, DOI: 10.7146/politica.v57i2.150402